

A Note on the Relation between Coagulation and Gelation Points of Sols.

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Gessner (*Koll. Chem. Beih.*, 1924, 19, 213) found in the case of vanadium pentoxide sol that more electrolyte is necessary to give a jelly of the sol in a definite period than to coagulate it. In this connection, I am submitting some of my observations regarding positively charged sols.

A known amount of the sol was mixed with different concentrations of electrolytes and the volume was kept constant in every case by the addition of water. The sols were allowed to stand for one hour, and the minimum amounts of electrolyte necessary to completely coagulate the sol and to give the jelly in the same period were noted. In the case of lyophilic jelly-forming sols, it is rather difficult to expect that the particles would settle down soon after coagulation, and therefore, the end points for coagulation were taken by filtering the sols and observing that no colloidal phase passes down in the filtrate at the point.

TABLE I.

Time of observation = 1 hour.

Sol.	Days dialysed.	Conc. per litre.	Amount of sol.		Electrolyte.	Coagulation point.		Gelation point.
			[c.c.]	[c.c.]		[c.c.]	[c.c.]	
1. Ferric arsenate	5	30 g.	2.5	5.0	N/5-KCl	0.35	0.45	
			3.0	5.0	"	0.40	0.50	
			1.5	5.0	N/200-K ₂ SO ₄	0.50	1.10	
			2.0	5.0	"	0.60	1.15	
			2.5	5.0	"	0.70	1.30	
2. Chromic arsenate	6	36.4	4.0	6.0	N/5-K ₂ SO ₄	0.90	1.10	
			4.0	6.0	N/10-K ₄ FeCy ₆	0.65	0.80	
3. Zirconium molybdate	5	14.48	4.0	6.0	N/20-KCl	0.39	0.40	
			4.0	6.0	N/50-K ₂ SO ₄	0.30	1.00	
4. Zirconium borate	4	24.72	4.0	6.0	N/4-KCl	0.80	1.30	
			4.0	6.0	N/10-K ₂ SO ₄	0.80	1.50	
5. Titanic acid	...	15.02	3.0	4.0	N/50-KCl	0.60	0.70	
					N/50-KBr	0.90	1.00	
					N/500-K ₂ CrO ₄	0.80	1.00	
					N/125-K ₂ SO ₄	0.30	0.50	
					N/1000-K ₂ FeCy ₆	0.40	0.50	
					N/1000-K ₄ FeCy ₆	0.30	0.40	

Similar results have been obtained with other sols both negatively and positively charged. From these results, it appears that a little more electrolyte is necessary to set a jelly than to coagulate the jelly-forming sol in the same time. The same amount of electrolyte which coagulates a sol in one hour would give the jelly in a period which varies with the purity of the sol. In the case of comparatively impure sols, the period of gelation has been extended from that of a few hours to 24 hours and even more. The effect of purity on the relation of coagulation and gelation points is illustrated in Table II.

A sol of ferric arsenate, containing much excess of ferric chloride was prepared and during the course of dialysis, its gelation and coagulation points and also the concentration of chloride ions were determined.

TABLE II.

Amount of sol taken = 3 c.c. Total volume = 5 c.c. Time = 1 hour.

Days dialysed.	Conc. per litre.	Conc. of chloride ions.	Molar conc. of K_2SO_4		<u>Gelation</u> <u>coagulation</u> ratio.
			to coagu- late.	to give jelly	
3	25.68 g	0.077N	0.08M	no jelly	—
10	22.31	0.018N	0.0015M	0.0025M	1.66
11	21.42	0.011N	0.0012M	0.0016M	1.33
12	21.67	0.0085N	0.0008M	0.0010M	1.25
13	23.01	0.0070N	0.0005M	0.00065M	1.10

The results recorded in this table show that as the sol becomes purer, and the concentration of chloride ions becomes less on dialysis, the ratio between gelation and coagulation concentrations approaches unity. In the case of very pure sols, gelation and coagulation points coincide with one another.

The difference between gelation and coagulation points is more marked when the sols are coagulated by bivalent ions than when by monovalent ions, as would be seen from Table III. The results are based on the figures given in the Table I.

TABLE III.

R is the ratio between the gelation and coagulation concentrations.

Sol.	R with KCl.	R with K_2SO_4 .
Ferric arsenate	$0.45/0.35=1.28$	$1.30/0.70=1.85$
Zirconium molybdate	$0.40/0.30=1.33$	$1.00/0.30=3.33$
Zirconium borate	$1.20/0.80=1.5$	$1.50/0.80=1.87$
Titanic acid	$0.70/0.60=1.16$	$0.50/0.30=1.66$

From these results, it would be seen that in all the cases, the value of R is greater when the coagulation is effected by potassium sulphate than when by potassium chloride.

The author wishes to express his indebtedness to Prof. N. R. Dhar for his very kind interest and guidance in the work.

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Received January 11, 1932.

